

INTERACTIVE METHODS IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785874>

Abstract. *The development of independent creative thinking of students is recognized as one of the most important indicators of the quality of the educational system. Because in this changing market economy, only a person who has the ability to think independently can solve his problems on his own. It is considered useful for oneself and for the family, everyone will have their own position in society. This ability is necessarily formed first in the family, and then in educational institutions.*

Keywords: *creative thinking, educational system, educational institutions, ability.*

Interactive methods are today one of the most popular types of pedagogical technologies. Interactive methods are a collaborative activity between student and teacher and basically encourage students to think. They teach to come to the right conclusions, introspection and practical application. The main task of the teacher here is to guide students, give direction and give the most correct conclusion. Interactive methods are also important because the teacher never sharply rejects the student's opinion, only gives the correct conclusion in time, and as a result, the student himself understands the mistake. This prevents them from depression and suppression of their thinking. Interactive methods are based on mutual respect between student and teacher. In any case, the teacher listens to the student's opinion and shows respect, and at the same time teaches the students to listen to each other. objections and additions are expressed in such words as "respected", "I agree with your opinion", "we also had some opinions". In a lesson organized in this way, the student feels that he is respected, and in such conditions he begins to think freely without any restrictions and can express it openly. At the same time, he learns respect others. Interactive methods provide students with constant activity. Students are not idle in the lesson; they are busy solving some problem related to the topic. The result is boredom. state is prevented. When using interactive methods, the teacher should first of all create a technological project of the lesson. For a technological design of the lesson, the teacher must be familiar with the strategies and methods of the interactive method. Today, a number of developed countries have accumulated rich experience in the use of pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative activity of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process, and the methods underlying this experience are unique. , The most important of today's teaching methods is the "interactive" method, now its rough translation is "interactive" in many cases, the term "interactive" actually comes from the English word "interactive", and "o" means "to interact", and it refers to the resolution of a dispute in an activity or method based on discussion, reflection, activity or teamwork. But we also witnessed the use of the term "interactive teaching methods" when we looked through some of the textbooks. The educational process is directly related to the teaching method. A methodology is not what technical means or books you use, but how your learning is organized, in other words, a teaching method is a form of interaction between a student and a teacher in the learning process. The process between the teacher and the student actually

shows that the student is connected with the goal of mastering certain knowledge, skills and abilities. If we take it broadly, then from the first days of training to this day, in a broad sense, a tripartite relationship between teacher and student has been formed and confirmed. It can be seen that in the methodological approach, we can divide all teacher methods into three groups:

1. Passive method.
2. Active method.
3. Interactive method

Each of these methodological approaches has its own characteristics. Below we consider methodological approaches. At the same time, we focus on the interactive methods of the teacher. The passive methodical approach is a form of communication between the student and the teacher. In this case, the teacher is the main driving force of the lesson, and students act as passive listeners. This method is expressed in quick independent questions and answers in classes, tests, tests and other methods. The passive method is considered the most inefficient way for students to master the educational material, but it also has its positive aspects. This type of lesson does not require much work. Allows you to find a large amount of educational material in a limited period of time. This type of lesson is widespread in higher educational institutions, and its most common form is a lecture. With an active-methodical approach, the teacher and the student interact with each other. During the lesson, the student becomes an active participant in the lesson, and not a passive listener. If the main driving figure in the passive method of teaching was the teacher, then in this method the student and the teacher have equal rights. Passive classes have an authoritarian learning style, while active methods have a democratic style. In the active and interactive approaches, the commonality is more noticeable. In general, we can consider interactive method as a form of more modern active methods. Unlike active methods, interactive methods are important because they focus on the interaction of the teacher and the student, as well as their active interaction with each other in the learning process. Below we will consider this method in more detail: With an interactive ("inter" - mutual, "action" - action - "means of interaction") methodological approach, students are completely immersed in the process of cognition and learning, they themselves can talk about what they know and think. Creates a sufficient basis for achieving the goal in interactive lessons. The teacher draws up a lesson plan (as a rule, interactive exercises and assignments are related to the material being studied). Interactive exercises and tasks in an interactive lesson performed by students, ordinary exercises and tasks in that in the process of their implementation not only the wound material is fixed, but new ones are also obtained. Also, these exercises and tasks are designed for an interactive approach, and in modern pedagogy a rich stock of them has been collected, among which are the following:

1. Creative task.
2. Work with small groups.
3. Educational games (role-playing, target and educational games).
4. Use of community resources (invitation of experts, excursions).
5. Social projects and teaching methods outside auditorium (social projects, radio and newspapers, films, stage works, songs and fairy tales).
6. Learning and consolidating new material (interactive lecture, working with visual aids, video and audio materials, "as a student-teacher", "everyone teaches everyone"), mosaic (jawed) use of questions, dialogue with a booklet).

7. Solving complex and contractual issues and problems (“school of thought”, “take a position”, developed techniques “POPS”, “one on one, together”, “change position”, “carousel”, “discussion in the style of a television talk show”, debates, symposium).

8. Problem-solution (“decision tree”, “brainstorming”, “case study”, “negotiation and mediation”)

By creative tasks, we mean those tasks that require participants not only to obtain simple information, but also to use a creative approach to it. Because the tasks at hand usually require several approaches to an unexplored element of large or small size. In an interactive teaching method, "brainstorming technology" can be used to organize discussion and free exchange of ideas between students to solve a problem situation. Teaching in small groups and in general teaching by the principle of teaching students to each other can also be understood. Therefore, as a result of using interactive methods, students learn to be more responsive, their vocabulary increases, scientific and theoretical knowledge is strengthened, which increases interest in the lesson and leads to the desire to mean the correct conclusion. Interactive methods are also important because the teacher never sharply rejects the student's opinion, only gives the correct conclusion in time, and as a result, the student himself understands the mistake. This prevents them from being depressed and suppressing their thinking.

Interactive methods are based on mutual respect between student and teacher. In any case, the teacher listens to the student's opinion and shows respect, and at the same time teaches the students to listen to each other. Objections and additions are expressed in such words as “respected”, “I agree with your opinion”, “we also had some opinions”. In a lesson organized in this way, the student feels that he is respected, and in such conditions he begins to think freely without any restrictions and can express it openly. Along with this, he learns to respect others. Interactive teaching methods. Interactive methods are one of the most popular types of pedagogical technologies today. Interactive methods are a joint activity of the student and the teacher and basically encourage students to think. They teach to come to the right conclusions, introspection and practical application. Interactive methods provide students with constant activity. Students are not idle in the lesson; they are busy solving some problem related to the topic. As a result, boredom is avoided. When using interactive methods, the teacher should, first of all, prepare a technological project of the lesson. For a technological design of the lesson, the teacher must be familiar with the strategies and methods of the interactive method. Today, a number of developed countries have accumulated rich experience in the use of pedagogical technologies that increase the educational and creative activity of students and guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process, and the methods underlying this experience are unique. The most important of modern teaching methods is the “interactive” method, now its rough translation is often called “interactive”, the term “interactive” actually comes from the English word “interactive”, which means “interaction”, “conflicting”. means mutual discussion, reflection or joint decision in an activity or method. But we also witnessed the use of the term "interactive teaching methods" when we looked through some of the textbooks. The educational process is directly related to the teaching method. Methodology is not what technical tools or books you use, but how your education is organized. In other words, the teaching method is a form of interaction between the student and the teacher in the learning process. Showing that the process between the teacher and the student actually connects the student with the aim of mastering certain knowledge, skills and abilities. The main task of the teacher here is to guide the students, give instructions and, most importantly, it is worth

taking broadly, from the first days of training to the present day, a tripartite relationship has developed between the teacher and the student in a broad sense, and it has found its confirmation. It can be seen that in the methodological approach, we can divide all teacher methods into three groups

Conclusion: In conclusion, in the article, we conclude the use of interactive technologies, forms and methods of teaching in the educational process is one of the most important areas for improving the training of students in a modern university. Experience allows us to draw the following conclusions:

- interactive learning contributes to the development of attention, observation, the ability to analyze, generalize;
- students learn to work in a team, participate in discussions and respect different points of view and ways of finding answers to problematic questions within the framework of educational tasks;
- the use of interactive technologies, forms and methods of organizing the learning process contributes to the achievement of interdisciplinary and meta-disciplinary results, personal and professional success in the future.

It is precisely the key ingredient in future endeavors that there will always be opportunities for pedagogical experimentation and research in education. This provides an inexhaustible potential for the development of competence and professionalism of all subjects of the educational process. At the same time, its practical implementation depends on the creation of pedagogical conditions and a special educational space in the university. In the long term, further attempts may prove to be a very useful contribution to education.

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